

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FORMATION OF GRAMMATICAL CONCEPTS OF NOUNS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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Annotation: Today country is giving the biggest attention and support to the education particularly mother tongue. There various innovative and pedagogical technologies in the way of teaching nouns in school. This article is devoted to the methods of teaching the nouns in school.

Key words; noun, pupil, teacher, education, affixation, object, grammatical category, functional forms, syntactic function, forming, sentence, possessive.

“A noun is a person, place, or thing.” Well... partially right, but there is much more. And knowing the definition of this basic part of speech only gets us so far. A noun is one of the independent word group.

They consists of the following:

1. Have the characteristic of forming a noun; worker, conversationalist, grower, gardener,
2. Have the characteristic of expressing number and quantity; boy- children, notebook- notebooks,
3. Have a possessive indicator; my father, your father, our father, their fathers,
4. Changes with agreement forms; school, of school, in school, to school, from school
5. In the sentence all the parts of the sentence appear.

According to the meaning, the nouns that express object or concepts can be imagined as objects are divided into proper nouns and common nouns. Names that distinguish one of the same objects or events are considered to be common nouns; Rustam, Olimjon, Jomboy, Mars, Venus, Boychibor, etc. Common nouns for objects of the same gender are common nouns; flowers, trees, pencils, notebooks.

The noun group has three different grammatical categories:

- Number category
- Ownership category
- Agreement category

There functional forms of the noun, which serve to express a certain additional grammatical meaning, to adapt to a syntactic function that is not characteristic of the categorical forms of nouns. There are three types of functional form specific of the according to its construction:

1. Synthetic form
2. Analytic form
3. Double and repeated form

Syntactic functional forms of nouns are divided into the following types according to their meaning and functions:

1. Diminutive form; fish, boy, girl.
2. Form of respect; mother, sister, father, brother, aunt

3. Form of ownership; brother's, school's
4. Location sign; in the village, in the sky, on the mountain
5. Border form; to the house, to the hill, to the garden, to the garden
6. Form of simile; like Ozod, like you

The analytical form of a noun is formed with the help of an auxiliary; with a pen, for my father. The double form of the noun expresses generalization, total meaning; pot-dish, melon. The repeated form of the noun expresses the meaning of the plural drop by drop, grain by grain. As a result of forming nouns, artificial nouns appear. Artificial nouns are created by means of affixation, composition and abbreviation. Affixation is the most productive way to form nouns, with the help of which personal nouns; painter, worker, schoolmate, jeweler, rice, farmer, noblemen, herdsmen, linguist, shoemaker, cook, cart driver, pigeon fancier, reader. Object-weapon nouns; picker, grower, bundle, spade, scraper, crop, throat, waterier, salter. Place names; almond garden, Uzbekistan, residence, office, meadow, pakhtaabad. Abstract nouns; goodness, cotton farming, trust, assembly, broadcasting, humanitarianism.

Compound nouns are formed when forming a noun by the method of composition; bracelet, bitter stone, triangle, sunflower, remover, production. When a noun is formed by the abbreviation method, abbreviated nouns are formed; UN, SamSU, UzME, and others. Noam Chomsky once said "The truth of the matter is that about 99 percent of teaching is about making. The students feel interested in the material. Then the other 1 percent has to do with your methods. And that's not just true of languages. It's true of every subject." Language is essential for communicating Ideas, build friendships, economic relationships and cultural ties. It distinguishes the differences and Celebrates the uniqueness of cultures. It shapes one's perception of a society's culture. Language Improves organization and adeptness. It unfastens one's minds to a mystical world of desire and dreams. Language advances our minds, and disposition. While using the innovative and pedagogical methods, teacher should focus on the age difference of classes for example In Kindergarten and 1st Grade, students will be introduced to nouns and learn more about what exactly they are. In these grades, students will learn about nouns being a person, place, or thing. Much of the learning at this point will involve determining what the noun is and deciding if it is a person, a place, or a thing. Activities such as the picture sorts and anchor chart above will help students pick out the nouns and categorize them as a person, place, or thing. With the anchor chart, students will see the types of words that count as nouns and have fun adding to the list. Repetition and discussing nouns in stories, sentences, and pictures is a great way to help young students learn about nouns.

In 1st grade, students dive into common and proper nouns. They will learn the difference between a common noun being a general person, place or thing and a proper noun being the actual name of the person, place, or thing. Students will also learn that common nouns are written in all lowercase letters while proper nouns begin with a capital letter. After teaching about common and proper nouns, it is time to teach your students about plural and irregular plural nouns. Plural and irregular plural nouns are learned in grades Kindergarten through 3rd grade, getting increasingly more complex as the grades progress. Kindergarten students will begin learning that adding an "s" or "es" to a word makes it plural, meaning more than one. Moreover, using different colored markers when making a noun or irregular is a good visual for students. Additionally, this skill will help them with their day-to-day language as they learn the difference between nouns, plural nouns, and irregular plural nouns. Word sorts and

activities such as the true or false cards above give students ample practice with determining the correct use and spelling of plural and irregular plural nouns at all ages. Next, your students will work on putting nouns and verbs together. Teaching your students about how nouns affect verb tenses is a key skill. Depending on whether the noun is singular or plural determines the type of verb you will use. This spinner activity gives the students practice with many noun-verb agreement scenarios. As a result, they will also analyze if the sentence makes sense. Nouns play one of the main role in sentence so we start teaching them in early age. The education which is repetited in all grade helps students to learn and recognize them easily. Why is noun so important? Nouns and pronouns are important because they identify the subjects and objects of sentences. You cannot make a complete sentence without a subject.

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